

ASPECTS OF PREVENTION OF NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE

¹Polykarpova N.V., ²Mirzakariimova F.R., ³Shamatov J.R.

¹Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

²Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

³Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

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Abstract. *Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is a pressing issue in modern healthcare, linked to the rising incidence of metabolic disorders and obesity. Preventing NAFLD requires a multi-level approach aimed at reducing risk factors and enhancing the overall health of the population.*

Keywords: *non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, metabolic syndrome, insulin resistance, visceral obesity, correction of metabolic states, lifestyle modification, weight reduction, physical activity, balanced diet.*

Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) is a nosological unit that has only recently become known in the medical community. The first mentions of it appeared in 1980 when H. Ludwig and his colleagues introduced the term “non-alcoholic steatohepatitis” (NASH) (Podymova S.D., La Brecque et al., 2014).

Today, NAFLD is considered one of the main causes of chronic liver disease. For a long time, this condition was largely overlooked by physicians across various specialties, as patients with NAFLD often presented with more severe comorbidities, such as type 2 diabetes (T2D) and metabolic syndrome. However, with the establishment of a link between insulin resistance and metabolic disorders, along with the understanding that the presence of NAFLD exacerbates the course of these diseases, interest in its study has significantly increased. As a result, a wealth of data regarding the pathogenesis, clinical picture, diagnosis, and treatment of NAFLD has accumulated (Volkova N.I., Porksheyan M.I., 2017).

Clinical manifestations of NAFLD often include symptoms of metabolic syndrome: visceral obesity, glucose metabolism disorders, dyslipidemia, and arterial hypertension. Some patients may report nonspecific complaints such as increased fatigue or discomfort in the right upper quadrant, unrelated to food intake. In cases where the disease progresses to liver cirrhosis (LC), symptoms of liver failure and portal hypertension may develop: abdominal distension, edema, hemorrhagic syndrome, and encephalopathy (McCullough A.J., 2013). Diagnoses often reveal obesity in patients with NAFLD.

It is important to note that clear guidelines for NAFLD therapy have not yet been developed. As this disease often accompanies obesity, T2D, and hyperlipidemia, it is necessary to correct these conditions, which implies treating metabolic syndrome (Lazebnik L.B., Zvenigorodskaya L.A., 2009). All contemporary guidelines emphasize the importance of lifestyle modification—weight reduction and increased physical activity—as the primary method for correcting metabolic risk factors. For effective treatment of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), gradual weight loss, a balanced diet with restrictions on fats and carbohydrates, and adequate physical exercise are recommended (Polunina T.E., 2014).

The development of steatosis and steatohepatitis is a complex process, and currently, several promising therapeutic schemes are being investigated, including the use of thiazolidinediones (TZDs). One option suggested is the administration of vitamin E at a dose of 400 mg per day, as there is evidence of its ability to improve liver histology. Treatment with pioglitazone is also considered for patients with biopsy-confirmed non-alcoholic steatohepatitis. Currently, a new potentially effective drug, GFT505—a dual agonist of PPAR α and δ receptors—is being studied (Polunina T.E., 2014).

Omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids are considered first-line medications for reducing triglyceride levels in patients with NAFLD; however, it is premature to call them primary therapeutic agents until randomized clinical trials are completed (Ivashkin V.T., Prof., Ed.). Statins are also recommended for correcting dyslipidemia in patients with NAFLD/NASH, but there is currently no data on the effect of statins on NAFLD (Ivashkin V.T., Prof., Ed.).

S-adenosylmethionine, formed from methionine in an ATP-dependent reaction, is involved in transmethylation. It is typically administered at a dose of 400 mg twice daily (Kalhan S.C. et al., 2011). The antioxidant properties of S-adenosylmethionine justify its use in NAFLD; however, convincing data on its long-term positive impact on biochemical and histological parameters in NASH have not yet been obtained (Ivashkin V.T., Prof., Ed.).

The efficacy of ursodeoxycholic acid in treating NAFLD, particularly NASH, has also been confirmed. The intake of UDCA at a dose of 15–30 mg/kg of body weight daily for 24–48 weeks leads to a significant reduction in serum transaminase activity (Zun Xiang et al., 2012). Nevertheless, there is no convincing data on its effect on non-inflammatory changes and liver fibrosis, as well as on the long-term prognosis of patients with NAFLD (Ivashkin V.T., Prof., Ed.).

Essential phospholipids possess antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties and can restore the integrity of cell membranes. Their use in NAFLD helps to reduce the degree of liver steatosis (according to ultrasound) and lower serum transaminase levels. However, convincing data on the long-term positive effects of essential phospholipids on the course of NASH are currently lacking (Ivashkin V.T., Prof., Ed.).

Thus, the directions for therapy in patients with NAFLD are based on the mechanisms of disease development. The main objectives for this category of patients include:

Correction of metabolic disorders:

Weight reduction (diet and physical activity);

Increased sensitivity of cellular receptors to insulin (metformin, thiazolidinediones);

Reduction of triglyceride levels (fibrates, statins);

Decrease in TNF- α concentration (pentoxifylline);

Antihypertensive therapy (angiotensin II receptor antagonists).

Treatment of oxidative stress:

Antioxidants and hepatoprotectors (vitamin E, silibinin, betaine, N-acetylcysteine, ursodeoxycholic acid, α -lipoic acid).

Restoration of intestinal microbiocenosis (eubiotics, probiotics, prebiotics).

Diet

For patients with overweight and obesity, it is necessary to reduce the overall calorie intake. Daily calorie intake should be tailored individually, taking into account body weight, age, sex, and level of physical activity, using specific formulas. Research shows that a weight reduction of 5–10% leads to a decrease in hepatosplenomegaly, ALT and AST activity, and correlates with the

regression of liver steatosis (Feldstein A.E. et al., 2006). It is important to note that rapid weight loss can trigger "acute" NASH, leading to portal fibrosis and central necrosis against a backdrop of significant inflammatory activity due to the influx of free fatty acids into the liver (Hamaguchi M. et al., 2005). A safe weight loss of 500 grams per week for children and 1600 grams per week for adults is recommended (Ratziu V. et al., 2015).

Additionally, all patients with NAFLD should adhere to the following recommendations:

Limit fat intake to 25–30% of total calorie intake.

Ensure the ratio of polyunsaturated to saturated fatty acids is greater than 1 (avoid butter, animal fats, and solid margarines; consume vegetable oils, seafood, fish, poultry, olives, and nuts according to energy needs).

Reduce the consumption of high-cholesterol foods (no more than 300 mg per day), excluding offal (liver, kidneys), caviar, egg yolks, smoked sausages, and fatty meats and dairy products.

Avoid fried and deep-fried foods.

Enrich the diet with vitamins and natural prebiotics (fruits, Jerusalem artichoke, leeks, artichokes).

For patients with HTG and type 2 diabetes, it is recommended to exclude simple carbohydrates and limit complex carbohydrates to achieve metabolic control.

Physical Activity

Physical activity is an essential component of the treatment for patients with NAFLD. It contributes to weight reduction and increases insulin sensitivity, facilitating the uptake of free fatty acids into muscle tissue for oxidation, which reduces insulin resistance (Feldstein A.E. et al., 2006). It is recommended to engage in physical exercises at least 3–4 times a week for a duration of 30–40 minutes.

Recent studies have shown that drinking mineral waters can positively affect metabolic processes in lipid and carbohydrate metabolism disorders in various groups of patients, including those suffering from metabolic syndrome often associated with NAFLD (Fedorova T.E. et al., 2012). The differentiated use of mineral waters and a bishofit aqueous solution is noted depending on the stage of the disease and the severity of metabolic disorders, as well as comorbidities such as digestive organ pathologies, type 2 diabetes, and hypertension.

I.B. Zabolotnaya and her colleagues agree with V.K. Frolkov's opinion on the need for further research on natural factors, including mineral waters, to develop indications for their use in this category of patients for the treatment and prevention of diseases.

Preventive Measures

To prevent diseases, it is important to maintain a proper diet, engage in regular physical activity, and avoid unjustified use of medications.

REFERENCES

1. Rinella M.E. Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease: a systematic review. *JAMA*. 2015. 313 (22): 2263–73.
2. Chalasani N, Younossi Z, Lavine JE, et al. The Diagnosis and Management of Non-alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease: Practice Guideline by the American Gastroenterological Association, American Association for the Study of Liver Diseases, and American College of Gastroenterology. *Gastroenterology*. 2012. 142 (7): 1592–1609.

3. Мирзакаримова, Ф., Поликарпова, Н., & Кадомцева, Л. (2024). ИНТЕГРИРОВАННЫЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЦЕНТР ДНЕВНОГО ПРЕБЫВАНИЯ. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*, 4(4), 115-120.
4. Кадомцева, Л. В., Поликарпова, Н. В., & Мирзакаримова, Ф. Р. (2024, April). Психологический Статус У Пациентов С Срк, Обучающихся В Школе Здоровья. In *International Congress on Biological, Physical And Chemical Studies (ITALY)* (pp. 43-44).
5. Каледа, С., & Мирзакаримова, Ф. (2023). Профилактика и факторы риска жирового гепатоза в практике семейного врача. *Актуальные проблемы современной фармакотерапии*, 1(1), 15-21.
6. Каледа, С., & Мирзакаримова, Ф. (2023). Дифференцированное лечение и профилактика бронхо-легочных и респираторных проявлений гастроэзофагеальной рефлюксной болезни. *Актуальные проблемы педиатрической фармакологии*, 1(1), 22-23.
7. Каледа, С., & Мирзакаримова, Ф. (2023). О влиянии методов народной медицины в лечении метаболического синдрома. *Актуальные проблемы педиатрической фармакологии*, 1(1), 56-58.
8. Назаров, А. А., & Мирзакаримова, Ф. Р. (2021). INFLUENCE OF SUBLINGUAL SPECIFIC IMMUNOTHERAPY ON THE DYNAMICS OF SENSITIZATION INDICATORS IN ATOPIC BRONCHIAL ASTHMA IN CHILDREN. *УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ*, (SPECIAL 1).
9. Норкобилов, И., Хасанова, М., Нурматов, М., Мирзакаримова, Ф., Одомбоев, Ш., Нурмухамедов, Х., ... & Хайдарова, С. (2021). Вредное воздействие пассивного курения на здоровье детей и взрослых. *Перспективы развития медицины*, 1(1), 189-189.
10. Vladimirovna, P. N., Abdulazizovna, V. T., & Petrovna, K. S. (2018). Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease-some aspects of prevention. *European science review*, 2(11-12), 136-138.
11. Поликарпова, Н. В., & Валиева, Т. А. (2015). Оценка роли печени в танатогенезе при материнской смертности. *Евразийский Союз Ученых*, (5-5 (14)), 62-63.
12. Кадомцева, Л., Бабаджанов, А., Пулатова, С., & Мирзакаримова, Ф. (2021). Основные факторы риска, патологии гепатопанкреатодуоденальной системы. *Журнал биомедицины и практики*, 1(2), 137-141.
13. Каледа, С. П. (2024). СТРАТИФИКАЦИЯ ФАКТОРОВ РИСКА ПОСТКОВИДНЫХ ОСЛОЖНЕНИЙ ЖКТ. ПРОФИЛАКТИКА И ЛЕЧЕНИЕ. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*, 4(4-1), 84-100.
14. Каледа, С. П., & Мирзакаримова, Ф. Р. ВЛИЯНИЕ ПЕРЕНЕСЕННОГО ИНФАРКТА МИОКАРДА НА КАЧЕСТВО ЖИЗНИ ПАЦИЕНТОВ. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКАЯ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ «COGNITIO»*, 2(3), 76.